

Potential of Electrospun Fibrous Scaffolds for Intestinal, Skin, and Lung Epithelial Tissue Modeling

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Herein, intestinal, skin, and pulmonary *in vitro* tissue models based on electrospun membranes of poly(ϵ -caprolactone) (PCL) and cellulose acetate (CA), cellulose acetate phthalate (CAP), ethylcellulose (EC), or methylcellulose (MC) are presented. Physicochemical characterization and biocompatibility analyses of the scaffolds are carried out using colorectal adenocarcinoma cells (intestine), keratinocytes and fibroblasts (skin), and bronchial and alveolar epithelial cells (lung). PCL, PCL:CA, and PCL:EC are composed of nanofibers, whereas PCL:CAP and PCL:MC scaffolds comprise a combination of micro- and nanofibers. PCL, PCL:CA, PCL:CAP, and PCL:EC samples demonstrate water contact angles greater than 90° and are, therefore, hydrophobic, while PCL:MC mats display a hydrophilic behavior. In intestinal models, cells adhere and proliferate on all scaffolds; in turn, studies with skin cell models reveal that PCL:CA and PCL:CAP blends outperform all other substrates. Lung cell models show that, while 16HBE cells adhere to and proliferate in PCL, PCL:CA, PCL:EC, and PCL:MC scaffolds, A549 cells only have the same biological response on PCL, PCL:CA, and PCL:MC. In summary, all fibrous meshes prepared are biocompatible toward most cell types tested, thus suggesting the potential of PCL-cellulose derivative blends as substrates suitable for *in vitro* epithelial tissue modeling and toxicity screening.

time-consuming and expensive process. It involves preclinical and clinical testing stages with stringent risk assessment requirements to ensure the clinical efficacy and safety of promising drugs in humans.^[1–3] The preclinical studies provide preliminary effectiveness, toxicity, pharmacokinetics, and safety evidence of potential drug candidates and include both *in vitro* experiments using standard 2D cell culture systems and/or more complex 3D organotypic tissue models, as well as *in vivo* experiments.^[2,4] This last stage is responsible for critically narrowing the number of lead compounds tested during first-in-human trials and avoiding late-stage failures that contribute to the high cost and attrition rate of drug development in the pharmaceutical industry.^[5,6] Indeed, the average cost of bringing a new drug to the market has been estimated to be \$1.3 billion.^[7] In addition, almost 95% of all drugs entering human trials fail, either due to unforeseen toxicity or lack of efficacy.^[6] Such limited clinical translation has mainly been linked to the lack of predictability in

the early preclinical phase testing.^[8] To accelerate pharmacological progress and fast-track the access to effective therapies, improvements need to be made at the level of preclinical models.^[9,10] Of these, *in vivo* studies exhibit several limitations. Although animal

1. Introduction

The development of novel active pharmaceutical ingredients, chemicals, and, more recently, nanoparticle-based drug formulations is a

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models are still extensively used as the gold-standard model prior to clinical testing, they often fail to predict human responses due to anatomical, physiological, and immunological species-specific differences.^[11,12] Furthermore, the raising ethical concerns and the current regulatory frameworks for the reduction, refinement, and replacement of animals in experiments (3R principle)^[13,14] have driven the development of improved engineered tissue models capable of replicating *in vivo* features and functionality for studying drug toxicity *in vitro*.

Drug delivery to a target site usually involves crossing biological barriers, including skin, lung, and intestinal barriers, for transdermal, inhalation, and oral drug delivery, respectively.^[15] Such epithelial barriers represent the primary sites of drug absorption and therefore constitute relevant predictive models for toxicity testing *in vitro*, as well as platforms for understanding ADME (absorption, distribution, metabolism, elimination) mechanisms and tissue barrier integrity and function. Conventionally, *in vitro* epithelium models consist of 2D cell culture systems where cell monolayers are grown on cell culture inserts with semi-permeable membranes that create the compartmentalization of different environments by establishing apical and basolateral regions.^[16,17] Besides replicating native *in vivo* structure, such compartmentalization enables the quantification of barrier permeability as a measure of barrier integrity, which can be used to monitor barrier dysfunction as a function of cytotoxicity, and to study drug crossing capacity.^[16] Recently, efforts regarding the implementation of more complex 3D biological systems such as multicellular spheroid and organoid technologies, as well as tissue-engineered based strategies, have been made to mimic epithelial tissues *in vitro* and create physiologically relevant alternatives that aim to bridge the gap between preclinical tests and *in vivo* outcomes.^[17–20]

Many biomaterial-based approaches focused on providing an improved spatial, biomechanical, and biochemical niche have been widely explored in the form of extracellular matrix (ECM) tissue analogues. Relevant examples include the use of electrospun fibrous scaffolds as permeable membranes for the culture of epithelial cells and tissues. Electrospinning is extensively employed in tissue engineering and regenerative medicine due to its capacity of generating fibrous scaffolds with nano-/microscaled features, which closely imitate the organization of ECM fibrillar proteins.^[21,22] Electrospun scaffolds typically have large surface area-to-volume ratios, high porosity, and pore interconnectivity,^[23–25] providing favorable conditions for cell adhesion, communication, nutrient and waste circulation. A basic electrospinning setup typically includes a programmable syringe pump, a conductive spinneret, a high-voltage power supply, and a collector (e.g., metal plate, rotating mandrel).^[26] Conventional, stainless steel needle spinnerets have been widely used for the production of electrospun fibers, but this traditional setup often has limited throughput, being unsuitable for scaffold mass production.^[27] Indeed, at a laboratory scale, the production rate of electrospun nanofibers is only about 0.01 to 0.1 g h⁻¹.^[28] Therefore, other electrospinning methods utilizing diverse spinneret designs have been developed to increase the productivity of this technique and attain high-throughput electrospun fiber generation.^[29] In particular, needleless electrospinning follows the same principle as traditional nozzle-based electrospinning, but it involves applying a strong electric field to the free surface of a polymer solution.

This results in a wider electrified area and, consequently, the formation of multiple Taylor cones and polymer jets.^[27,30] Besides its higher productivity rates, this method is also free from issues commonly observed in conventional electrospinning, such as needle clogging.^[27]

An important benefit of electrospun fiber production resides in the wide variety of biomaterials that can be processed using this technique, including both natural and synthetic polymers.^[31] Accordingly, in this work, blend scaffolds incorporating both poly(ϵ -caprolactone) (PCL) and cellulose derivatives were fabricated for the development of cell culture substrates suitable for *in vitro* epithelial tissue models. PCL is one of the most frequently used synthetic polymers in bioengineering and, specifically, in electrospinning, constituting a biocompatible, biodegradable, and cost-effective polyester.^[32,33] Importantly, it is commercially available in a broad range of molecular weights and soluble in numerous organic solvents, thus allowing the preparation of electrospun fibers with differing properties.^[33] It is, however, hydrophobic, implying that its mixture with hydrophilic polymers may be necessary for appropriate cell attachment and proliferation. In fact, this polymer easily forms blends and composites with other materials, providing an excellent base for mechanical support that can be further enhanced by combination with polymers displaying other properties of interest.^[34]

In turn, cellulose is known as the most abundant organic polymer on the planet, constituting an ample and sustainable source of raw material.^[35–37] It is composed of linear chains of repeating glucose monomers, which organize into fibrils and, subsequently, bundles, giving rise to a highly organized hierarchical structure.^[36] This tightly packed conformation is attained by means of intra- and intermolecular hydrogen bonds, electrostatic and van der Waals forces, resulting in exceptional mechanical properties and water insolubility, in spite of the hydrophilic character of cellulose chains.^[35,36] While it is biocompatible, biodegradable, and noncytotoxic, cellulose is only poorly degraded in the human organism, limiting its biological applicability, as it cannot be replaced by newly synthesized ECM and regenerated tissue.^[35,38,39] Nonetheless, it is amenable to chemical modification, giving rise to a plethora of cellulose derivatives with varying physicochemical and mechanical properties that can be tailored to specific biomedical applications. Such chemical modifications are usually performed by functionalizing the free hydroxyl groups of the anhydroglucose units with other chemical moieties via etherification or esterification reactions.^[36] Cellulose esters include cellulose acetate (CA) and cellulose acetate phthalate (CAP), whereas ethylcellulose (EC) and methylcellulose (MC) are important examples of cellulose ethers (**Figure 1**).

In the present study, each of these four cellulose derivatives was combined with PCL in electrospun membranes for intestinal, skin, and lung *in vitro* modeling. Nanofibrous scaffolds were manufactured via needleless electrospinning and characterized in terms of fiber morphology, chemical composition, and wettability. Biocompatibility analyses were performed in intestinal, skin, and lung cells to evaluate the biological response induced by the different biomaterial combinations. Based on these data, the potential of PCL and cellulose derivative blend scaffolds as simple, yet physiologically relevant, *in vitro* epithelial tissue modeling platforms was assessed.

Figure 1. Molecular structure of the cellulose derivatives used in this work.

2. Results

2.1. Electrospun Scaffold Characterization

2.1.1. Scanning Electron Microscopy

The architecture and cross-sections of the produced scaffolds were analyzed using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and are displayed in **Figure 2**, along with the corresponding fiber diameter histograms. PCL, PCL:CA, PCL:EC, and PCL:MC mats exhibited a nonwoven morphology with smooth fibers and a negligible number of defects. Conversely, PCL:CAP showed rough fibers in a nonwoven mat with a scarce number of imperfections. Fiber diameter histograms of PCL, PCL:CA, PCL:CAP, and PCL:EC displayed a skewed unimodal frequency distribution ranging between 100 and 1000, 100 and 700, 400 and 2000, and 100 and 600 nm, respectively. In contrast, an asymmetrical bimodal fiber diameter distribution was found for PCL:MC. The left peak ranged from 100 to 600 nm and the right one from 800 to 1320 nm. According to these results, PCL, PCL:CA and PCL:EC were composed of nanofibers, while PCL:CAP and PCL:MC consisted mainly of nanofibers as well as smaller quantities of microfibrils. The mean fiber diameters of electrospun PCL, PCL:CA, PCL:CAP, PCL:EC, and PCL:MC mats were found to be 517 ± 210 , 348 ± 120 , 681 ± 221 , 302 ± 103 , and 345 ± 231 nm, respectively, with membrane thicknesses varying between 61.5 and 173.7 μm . The respective mean pore areas were 1.99 ± 1.70 , 1.67 ± 1.27 , 1.57 ± 0.95 , 1.33 ± 0.89 , and $1.56 \pm 1.22 \mu\text{m}^2$ (**Table 1**).

2.1.2. Fourier Transform Infrared Analysis

Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) analysis was performed to identify specific chemical groups capable of confirming the presence of PCL and cellulose derivatives in the obtained scaffolds.^[40] **Figure 3A** shows the FTIR spectra of the pristine

PCL and the blends of PCL with the different cellulose derivatives. All FTIR profiles exhibited peaks at 2944, 2866, 1721, 1367, 1239, 1164, and 1044 cm^{-1} , corresponding to asymmetric stretching of CH_2 , symmetric stretching of CH_2 , a carbonyl group ($\text{C}=\text{O}$) stretch band, a CH_3 peak, asymmetric stretching of $\text{C}-\text{O}-\text{C}$, symmetric stretching of $\text{C}-\text{O}-\text{C}$ and $\text{C}-\text{O}$ stretching, respectively.^[41–44] These peaks match with characteristic peaks of PCL, thus demonstrating its presence in all the prepared formulations. Of note, it is possible that overlaps occur between PCL and cellulose derivatives, since they share identical functional groups, namely CH_2 , CH_3 , and $\text{C}-\text{O}-\text{C}$ moieties.

Looking closely into the region between 3100 and 2700 cm^{-1} , PCL exhibited 2 peaks – 2944 and 2866 cm^{-1} – which also appeared in all other formulations (**Figure 3B**). Nevertheless, the latter showed some specific peaks and peak modifications that were not found in plain PCL. In the PCL:CA spectrum, the peak at 2944 cm^{-1} is broader and two additional peaks were revealed at 2918 and 2851 cm^{-1} , both corresponding to the $\text{C}-\text{H}$ stretching vibration from cellulose,^[45] which were also observed in PCL:MC. PCL:CAP presented a similar spectrum to that of PCL:CA, with an additional broad shoulder at 2921 cm^{-1} , and PCL:EC displayed a peak at 2972 cm^{-1} corresponding to $\text{C}-\text{H}$ stretching,^[46] as well as a peak at 2944 cm^{-1} broader than that of plain PCL. Furthermore, in the region between 1800 and 1630 cm^{-1} (**Figure 3C**), a peak at 1721 cm^{-1} ascribed to the carbonyl group ($\text{C}=\text{O}$) stretch band from PCL appeared, as expected, in all spectra. PCL:CA and PCL:CAP spectra manifested an additional peak at 1756 cm^{-1} which was associated with the stretching of the carbonyl group ($\text{C}=\text{O}$) of the cellulose esters.^[47]

Finally, it was verified that, in the region between 1325 and 900 cm^{-1} (**Figure 3D**), the peak at 1164 cm^{-1} had a higher intensity than the peak at 1239 cm^{-1} in plain PCL, PCL:EC, and PCL:MC scaffolds, whereas in PCL:CA and PCL:CAP the opposite situation occurred. This indicates that there are differences among the formulations arising from the distinct ratios of the corresponding bond vibrations. Moreover, the PCL:CAP spectrum showed an additional peak at 787 cm^{-1} , corresponding to aromatic $\text{C}-\text{H}$ vibrations.^[48]

2.1.3. Contact Angle Measurements

The wettability of a material's surface is a critical parameter in the development of tissue-engineered biomaterials, since it highly influences protein adsorption and cell adhesion.^[49–51] Wettability is usually determined by the contact angle established between the surface of a liquid and the outline of the scaffold's surface. **Figure 4** presents the water contact angles of the electrospun scaffolds of PCL, PCL:CA, PCL:CAP, PCL:EC and PCL:MC after 0, 10, 30, and 60 s of droplet deposition. PCL, PCL:CA, PCL:CAP, and PCL:EC samples were found to have angles greater than 90° during the entire experimental period and, therefore, are considered hydrophobic (poor wettability). Contrarily, PCL:MC blends exhibited contact angles of less than 90° and are, thus, hydrophilic (good wettability). The decreasing trend of the water contact angle values over time in these scaffolds is due to the polymeric materials' water absorption capacity.^[52] PCL:MC revealed significant differences compared to all other scaffolds, except PCL:CAP at 0 s. Within the group of scaffolds with poor wettability, no categorization in terms of hydrophobicity could be inferred between different formulations, as the difference

Figure 2. Scaffold morphology and fiber diameter measurements. Left column: scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of the electrospun scaffold surfaces. Images were acquired at a magnification of 5000 \times ; scale bars: 10 μm . Center column: SEM images of the electrospun scaffold cross-sections. Images were acquired at a magnification of 800 \times ; scale bars: 30 μm . Right column: fiber diameter distributions.

Table 1. Morphological features of the different types of scaffolds. Diameter and pore area were measured manually using Fiji/ImageJ software. Data represent mean \pm SD.

Scaffold material	Mean diameter [nm]	Scaffold thickness [μm]	Mean pore area [μm^2]
PCL	517 \pm 210	173.7 \pm 1.8	1.99 \pm 1.70
PCL:CA	348 \pm 120	151.3 \pm 2.4	1.67 \pm 1.27
PCL:CAP	681 \pm 221	61.5 \pm 7.3	1.57 \pm 0.95
PCL:EC	302 \pm 103	96.9 \pm 0.7	1.33 \pm 0.89
PCL:MC	345 \pm 231	150.3 \pm 9.9	1.56 \pm 1.22

between the mean contact angle of each formulation is small and, hence, no significant differences were found.

2.2. In vitro Biocompatibility of Electrospun Fibrous Scaffolds Toward Intestinal, Skin, and Lung Cells

The in vitro biocompatibility of PCL and cellulose-derivative fibrous scaffolds toward intestinal, skin, and lung cells was investigated through cell viability, proliferation, and adhesion studies. To this end, human colorectal adenocarcinoma cells (Caco-2 cell line), murine dermal fibroblasts (3T3 cell line) and epidermal keratinocytes (XB2 cell line), and human bronchial epithelial (16HBE cell

Figure 3. FTIR spectra of the electrospun pristine PCL and PCL:cellulose derivative scaffolds, detailed according to the identified peaks and corresponding functional groups. A) Full spectra (region 4000–500 cm^{-1}). B) Close-up of the region between 3100 and 2700 cm^{-1} . C) Close-up of the region between 1800 and 1630 cm^{-1} . D) Close-up of the region between 1325 and 900 cm^{-1} .

line) and adenocarcinoma alveolar epithelial cells (A549 cell line) were seeded onto the prepared fibrous scaffolds (PCL, PCL:CA, PCL:CAP, PCL:EC and PCL:MC) and cultured for up to 14 or 21 days under optimized culture conditions. During preliminary investigations, it was found that PCL:CAP blend scaffolds were not conducive to 16HBE or A549 cell adhesion and proliferation, and PCL:EC electrospun membranes were only capable of supporting 16HBE cell growth. Therefore, both cell lines were tested on PCL, PCL:CA, and PCL:MC formulations, and PCL:EC blends were only used for 16HBE cell biocompatibility analysis.

2.2.1. Cell Metabolic Activity

The metabolic activity of Caco-2 cells was assessed using the MTS assay on days 1, 3, 7, 14, and 21 of cell cultivation. The

results are presented in **Figure 5A**. Caco-2 cell metabolic activity showed a fluctuating behavior throughout the cultivation period in all scaffolds, except when cultured on PCL:MC. After one day of culture, PCL:CA scaffolds were shown to induce significantly higher Caco-2 cell metabolic activity than PCL ($p = 0.0205$), PCL:EC ($p = 0.0249$) and PCL:MC ($p = 0.0017$). The lowest metabolic activity values were found on days 1 and 3 for PCL:MC scaffolds, and it was significantly lower than PCL ($p = 0.0036$, day 3), PCL:CA ($p = 0.0038$, day 3) and PCL:EC ($p < 0.0001$, day 3) formulations. After 14 days of in vitro culture, Caco-2 cells grown on PCL:EC scaffolds exhibited higher metabolic activity than on any other scaffold and this condition was found to be statistically relevant when compared to PCL:MC ($p = 0.0081$), PCL:CA ($p = 0.0019$) and PCL ($p = 0.0261$). From day 14 onwards, a considerable decrease in the cells' metabolic activity was observed for PCL,

Figure 4. Water contact angles of PCL, PCL:CA, PCL:CAP, PCL:EC, PCL:MC electrospun fibrous membranes. A) Measurements performed at 0, 10, 30, and 60 s after droplet deposition. Data represent mean \pm SD ($n \geq 17$). Nonparametric Kruskal–Wallis test with Dunn’s post-hoc analysis, $*p < 0.05$, $***p < 0.001$ and $****p < 0.0001$. B) Representative images of the contact angles measured at 0 s for PCL, PCL:CA, PCL:CAP, and PCL:EC scaffolds, and at 0, 10, 30, and 60 s for PCL:MC. Contact angle images of PCL:MC samples at different timepoints are displayed to demonstrate the rapid absorption of the water droplet over time. Scale bars: 0.5 mm.

PCL:CAP and PCL:EC meshes. Interestingly, a steady rise in cell metabolic activity occurred from day 3 onwards in PCL:MC blends, reaching the highest values among all scaffolds on day 21. In fact, on day 21, the metabolic activity on PCL:MC was statistically higher than PCL ($p = 0.0001$), PCL:CAP ($p = 0.002$) and PCL:EC ($p = 0.0315$) meshes. Overall, all scaffolds were able to sustain metabolically active Caco-2 cells over the investigated period.

For dermal fibroblasts, during the first week of in vitro culture, scaffolds prepared from the PCL:CA and PCL:CAP blends exhibited superior properties in stimulating fibroblasts’ metabolic activity, with PCL:CA standing out ($p = 0.0052$, day 7) Figure 5B. Nevertheless, on day 14, this trend shifted, as both plain PCL and PCL:MC scaffolds demonstrated an increased ability to promote fibroblasts metabolic activity, comparable to that of PCL:CA and PCL:CAP. Interestingly, PCL:EC substrates showed a consistently lower ability to support fibroblasts metabolic activity throughout the entire culture period and even presented a considerably greater standard deviation on day 14. Similarly,

for epidermal keratinocytes, the MTS profile revealed that PCL:CA and PCL:CAP scaffolds lead to significantly higher cell metabolic activity than other cellulose blends and plain PCL scaffolds at most timepoints selected Figure 5C. Although there was a considerable increase in cell metabolic activity from day 7 to day 14 in all conditions, this increase was more significant in the case of PCL:CA and PCL:CAP scaffolds, which shows their outperformance. Yet again, PCL:EC and PCL:MC blends could not similarly support keratinocytes’ metabolic activity, leading to the lowest observed values.

In the case of 16HBE and A549 cells, no significant differences were found between the different cell culture substrates on days 1 or 3 for either cell line. Intriguingly, A549 cell metabolic activity decreased from day 1 to day 3 in all experimental conditions. After a week of in vitro culture, 16HBE cell metabolic activity was significantly lower in PCL scaffolds compared to all other electrospun substrates, particularly PCL:EC ($p = 0.0015$, Figure 5D). A549 cells seemed to partially recover their metabolic

Figure 5. Metabolic activity of: A) Caco-2, B) 3T3, C) XB2, D) 16HBE, and E) A549 cells seeded on PCL and PCL:cellulose derivative blend electrospun scaffolds, as assessed by an MTS assay on days 1, 3, 7, 14, and 21 (D1-D21) of culture. Data represent mean \pm SD ($n \geq 3$). Symbols *, #, +, ϕ , and Δ denote statistically significant differences observed on days 1, 3, 7, 14, and 21, respectively. One-way ANOVA with Tukey's post hoc analysis, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$, **** $p < 0.0001$ (analogous for the other symbols).

activity levels on day 7, in which the performance of plain PCL was inferior to that of PCL:MC formulations ($p = 0.0487$), but no significant differences from PCL:CA were found ($p = 0.7132$, Figure 5E). Remarkably, the two cell lines also appeared to behave distinctively from days 7 to 14: 16HBE cell metabolic activity rose in plain PCL scaffolds during the second

week of culture, but fell substantially in PCL:CA, PCL:EC and PCL:MC substrates. Conversely, A549 cells demonstrated an increment in cell viability at day 14 for all experimental conditions tested, with significantly higher values of metabolic activity in PCL:MC than in PCL ($p = 0.027$) and PCL:CA ($p = 0.0217$) scaffolds.

2.2.2. Cell Proliferation

dsDNA quantification data collected on days 1, 3, 7, 14, and 21 are depicted in **Figure 6**. On days 1 and 3, the amount of dsDNA of Caco-2 cells cultured on PCL:EC scaffolds was significantly lower than the remaining samples on day 1 and PCL:CA on day 3 ($p=0.0139$). A continuous increase in dsDNA was observed on all cellulose-based scaffolds at least until day 14.

The maximum dsDNA values were found after 21 days for Caco-2 cells cultured on PCL, PCL:CAP and PCL:MC electrospun mats. Cells grown on PCL:CA and PCL:EC meshes exhibited a slight decrease in dsDNA suggesting that they reached confluence on day 14. On the same day, the dsDNA amounts of Caco-2 cells cultured on PCL:CA scaffolds were significantly superior to those on PCL:MC scaffolds ($p=0.0049$). Lower dsDNA quantities were found for cells cultured on PCL:EC

Figure 6. dsDNA quantification of: A) Caco-2, B) 3T3, C) XB2, D) 16HBE, and E) A549 cells seeded on PCL and PCL:cellulose derivative blend electrospun scaffolds, as assessed by dsDNA High-Sensitivity or Quant-iT PicoGreen kit assays on days 1, 3, 7, 14, and 21 (D1-D21) of culture. Data represent mean \pm SD ($n \geq 3$). Symbols *, #, +, ϕ , and Δ denote statistically significant differences observed on days 1, 3, 7, 14, and 21, respectively. One-way ANOVA with Tukey's post hoc analysis, $*p < 0.05$, $**p < 0.01$, $***p < 0.001$, $****p < 0.0001$ (analogous for the other symbols).

and PCL:MC meshes during the whole experiment, while PCL:CA and PCL:CAP blends allowed a continuous cell growth and maximum dsDNA contents similar to those of PCL.

Regarding dermal fibroblasts, the proliferation data acquired on the days corresponding to the MTS assay showed a similar pattern to the metabolic activity of seeded cells (Figure 6B). Regardless of the condition, there was a considerable increase in the amount of dsDNA detected from day 1 to day 3, which suggests that all substrates could promote cell recovery and proliferation after seeding. Furthermore, until day 7, fibroblasts seeded on PCL:CA, PCL:CAP, and plain PCL exhibited a significantly higher dsDNA content, indicating their increased proliferation on these substrates. This trend was maintained until day 14 of the experiment, when fibroblasts seeded on PCL:MC scaffolds showed significantly higher dsDNA content than those seeded on PCL:EC electrospun fibers ($p < 0.0001$), and comparable to that of cells cultured on PCL, PCL:CA, and PCL:CAP mats. In the case of epidermal keratinocytes, a slightly different pattern was found for the proliferation data relatively to the cells' MTS profile – Figure 6C. Although on earlier timepoints PCL:CA, PCL:CAP, and even plain PCL scaffolds led to a significantly higher dsDNA content compared to the alkyl-substituted cellulose derivative fibers (PCL:EC and PCL:MC), on day 14 of cell culture, PCL:CAP membranes outperformed all other substrates in terms of keratinocyte proliferation. It is also interesting to point out that the dsDNA content of keratinocytes seeded on PCL:CA scaffolds decreased from day 7 to day 14. Hence, despite being metabolically active, keratinocytes

might have reached confluency, which translated into decreased cell proliferation.

For lung cells, overall, dsDNA quantification results largely agree with the conclusions gathered from cell metabolic activity data: 16HBE cells were able to grow continuously in every formulation up to day 7, in which the dsDNA amounts were significantly lower in PCL fibrous mats compared to all other formulations, but a drastic reduction of dsDNA was recorded between days 7 and 14 for PCL:CA, PCL:EC, and PCL:MC meshes (Figure 6D). In turn, dsDNA amounts of A549 cells were nearly undetectable on days 1 and 3 in all scaffolds (Figure 6E), increasing considerably after a week of culture. On day 7, no differences were found among the three electrospun formulations, but, after two weeks of culture, dsDNA quantities in PCL:MC substrates significantly surpassed those of plain PCL ($p = 0.0175$).

2.2.3. Cell Adhesion, Distribution, and Morphology

To investigate the adhesion and distribution of Caco-2 cells on PCL and cellulose derivative scaffolds, cell internal membranes were labeled using fluorescent staining and detected *via* confocal microscopy on days 1, 7, 14, and 21. Caco-2 cells adhered to all investigated fibers/matrices (Figure 7). On day 1, Caco-2 cells were mainly organized in clusters. After that, they were able to proliferate and grow, forming a continuous monolayer and reaching confluence on day 14. As of this day, a typical polygonal, cobblestone morphology was noticeable, which is characteristic of the apical pole of the epithelial cells.^[53] An undulated cell layer was detected on PCL and PCL:CAP

Figure 7. Adhesion and distribution of Caco-2 cells at days 1, 7, 14, and 21 (D1-D21) of cell culture on PCL and cellulose-derivative electrospun scaffolds. Images show representative 2D projections of CLSM stack images on planes $x-y$ (square images) and $y-z$ (rectangular images) of cells' internal membranes labeled with DiOC₆(3) (green color). Nuclei were counterstained with propidium iodide (PI, red color). Objective 40×; scale bars: 50 μm.

scaffolds on day 14 and on PCL:MC on day 21, as can be seen in y-z planes in Figure 7. These data showed consistency with the data obtained in the dsDNA quantification studies.

Regarding skin cell models, DiOC₆(3) staining of cell internal membranes showed that both 3T3 fibroblasts and XB2 keratinocytes

could adhere and proliferate on all types of scaffolds considered right from the beginning of the experiment and no considerable cell loss was observed until the end of the culture period (Figure 8A,B). In fact, there was an increase in cell number from day 1 to day 14 in all conditions and cell types, as clear by the less

Figure 8. Adhesion and distribution of: A) 3T3 and B) XB2 skin cells at days 1, 7, and 14 (D1-D14) of cell culture on PCL and cellulose-derivative electrospun scaffolds. Images show representative 2D projections of CLSM stack images of cells' internal membranes labeled with DiOC₆(3) (green color). Nuclei were counterstained with propidium iodide (PI, red color). Objective 20 \times ; scale bars: 50 μ m.

pronounced boundaries and higher cell density on the last day of the experiment. Despite this, there were important differences in terms of cell arrangement and morphology depending on the type of electrospun fibers being considered. While dermal fibroblasts seeded on PCL:CA, PCL:CAP, and PCL mats were homogeneously distributed throughout the surface of the meshes, when cultured on PCL:EC and PCL:MC scaffolds, these cells organized into round aggregates and partly lost their flat and elongated shape typical of epithelial fibroblast culture. Interestingly, after two weeks of in vitro cell culture, fibroblasts seeded on plain PCL also lost their spindle-like shape as was the case for cells cultured on PCL:CA and PCL:CAP. Similarly, XB2 keratinocytes adopted a clustered morphology when cultivated on PCL:EC and PCL:MC meshes but presented a rather uniform distribution throughout the surface when considering PCL:CA, PCL:CAP, and pristine PCL scaffolds. Importantly, already after 1 week of culture, keratinocytes showed a typical cobblestone epithelial growth pattern on all substrates.

ActinGreen/NucBlue staining of 16HBE cells cultured on PCL and PCL:cellulose derivative scaffolds revealed that they were capable of growing in all substrates tested during the first week of in vitro culture, but, as expected, there was a substantial loss of cells on day 14 on all formulations except for plain PCL matrices (Figure 9A). On the first day of culture, 16HBE cells were mainly scattered individually or in small aggregates throughout the surface of the scaffolds, and these aggregates seemed to grow in size during the first week of culture and displayed a typical epithelial cobblestone morphology. After 14 days, seemingly viable cells could still be observed only in PCL scaffolds, revealing extensive cell death for PCL:CA, PCL:EC, and PCL:MC formulations for culture periods over one week. Conversely, A549 cells grew slowly on these scaffolds, as proven by the extremely low cell densities observed in the first two timepoints (Figure 9B) and supported by the cell viability and proliferation results. As a matter of fact, A549 cell numbers seemed to diminish in all electrospun matrices tested from days 1 to 7. In spite of this, A549 cells were able to recover on the three fibrous meshes, though only partial confluency was achieved by day 14 of culture.

3. Discussion

Basement membranes are ultrathin sheets of ECM that underlie epithelial layers and whose primary functions are to provide structural support and a surface for cell attachment, act as a diffusion barrier, and help regulate cell growth.^[54,55] These membranes are generally composed of two layers: the basal lamina, secreted by epithelial cells, and the reticular lamina, which anchors the basal lamina to the underlying connective tissue and is secreted by fibroblasts.^[56,57] In the latter, collagenous fibrils, its main component, are embedded in a proteoglycan-rich ground substance and assembled in a multi-hierarchical structure that provides structural support to the basement membrane.^[58,59] In this study, we draw on the fibrous structure of this reticular layer to develop porous membranes that can provide mechanical support for cell growth and be used as a simple and cost-effective method for in vitro toxicological screening.

Nonwoven PCL:cellulose derivative electrospun mats were obtained due to the whipping motion of the jet path combined

with the low-medium rotating speed of the electrospinning set drum (600 rpm). Since intestinal, pulmonary, and skin epithelial cells are not aligned, there was no need to develop orientated scaffolds, making it possible to benefit from the isotropy of random fiber scaffolds.^[60] Scaffold topography is an important feature in cell adhesion, as cells are capable of mechanotransduction, through which they recognize topographical and mechanical signals via surface receptors (e.g., integrins) and convert these cues into biochemical signaling, thereby modulating cell adhesion, cytoskeletal arrangement, and migration.^[61] Fibrous scaffolds were produced from PCL and PCL:CA, PCL:CAP, PCL:EC, and PCL:MC blends, obtaining a nanoscale topography similar to that of the basement membrane. Several studies have demonstrated the advantages of nanofibers in cell adhesion and proliferation^[62–66] and that cells organize better around fibers with diameters smaller than their own.^[67] Nano- and microfiber combined scaffolds, such as those of PCL:CAP and PCL:MC, have also been pointed out as enhancers of cell adhesion and proliferation. Rampichová et al. showed that hybrid nano- and microfibrillar scaffolds prepared using a melt-blown method were able to better stimulate human mesenchymal stem cell adhesion, proliferation, and osteogenic differentiation than predominantly microfibrillar or nanofibrillar scaffolds.^[68] The different orders of magnitude of the fiber diameters between distinct formulations must have been caused, during the electrospinning process, by the polymer solution parameters, since the environmental and processing parameters were identical for all formulations.^[27] Cellulose derivatives' molecular weight and molecular chain length are two of these factors that can affect the viscosity of the solution, which in turn influences the diameter of the fibers, making them thicker if solution viscosity is high. Rheological measurements of the solutions prior to electrospinning could dictate if the reason behind the thicker diameters of PCL:CAP and PCL:MC samples was indeed the higher viscosity of these solutions.

When designing a porous membrane for a barrier or co-culture model, numerous scaffold features must be considered to improve the physiological relevance of the biomimetic tissue. A particularly important feature is the pore size, as it can determine whether cells interact with the surface (lower than 1 μm), communicate with each other (between 1 and 3 μm) or can penetrate the membrane/scaffold (3–12 μm).^[69] The pore area of the studied blends, lower than 2 μm^2 , was too small to allow the transmigration of cells into the scaffold, which indicates that cells will grow as monolayers on the membranes, without much penetration into them, as intended.

According to the literature, cells are more likely to adhere to hydrophilic biomaterials,^[70] as cell adhesion is mediated by the a priori adhesion of proteins to the surface, and these proteins, when exposed to a hydrophobic surface, undergo a conformational change leading to a decrease in accessible focal adhesion sites.^[71] Optimal cell adhesion in polymeric surfaces has been reported for water contact angles between 40° and 70°; however, this depends on several factors, including cell type, incubation time, culture conditions, surface chemistry, and topography.^[72] Hydrophobic groups or chains in the constituent polymers of the samples of PCL, PCL:CA, PCL:CAP, and PCL:EC were indicative of the poor wettability results obtained for these samples: PCL due to its aliphatic chains, CA to acetyl groups,^[73] CAP to acetyl groups and the alkyl chain on the phthalate group,^[74] and EC to

Figure 9. Adhesion and distribution of: A) 16HBE and B) A549 cells at days 1, 7, and 14 (D1-D14) of culture on PCL and cellulose-derivative electrospun scaffolds. Images show representative 2D projections of CLSM stack images of the cellular cytoskeleton stained with ActinGreen (phalloidin, green color). Nuclei were counterstained with NucBlue (DAPI, blue color). Objective 20 \times ; scale bars: 50 μ m.

ethyl groups.^[75] Conversely, PCL:MC was found to exhibit a hydrophilic behavior, which can be attributed to the methoxy groups of the MC polymer. These methoxy groups disturb the establishment of intermolecular hydrogen bonds and allow the penetration of water molecules into the polysaccharide structure

if the degree of substitution is lower than 2.5, which is the case of the MC polymer used in this study.^[76]

While combinations of PCL and cellulose derivatives in electrospun scaffolds are uncommon in the literature, they have been previously reported for PCL and CA,^[44,77] PCL and EC,^[78] and

PCL and MC mixtures.^[79] To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study comparing the potential of four different cellulose derivatives, including cellulose esters and ethers, for the fabrication of biocompatible scaffolds applied to in vitro epithelial tissue modeling for toxicological screening. The literature is still limited to a handful of studies focusing on the production and use of electrospun scaffolds as models of the intestinal epithelium and their biocompatibility with intestinal cell lines such as Caco-2 cells. For instance, in a study by Hu et al., electrospun poly (lactic acid) (PLA) matrices were prepared to reproduce the basement membrane and ECM of the intestinal epithelium. The results demonstrated enhanced differentiation and proliferation of Caco-2 cells and promoted the formation of an intact and mature monolayer, in fact showing results more similar to in vivo conditions than those obtained with commercial Transwells.^[80] In another work, the cultivation of Caco-2 cells on collagen-coated polyethylene terephthalate (PET) nanofibrous membranes showed the potential to investigate passive drug absorption.^[81] The in vitro studies conducted in this work revealed that all the formulated scaffolds are, in principle, suitable for Caco-2 cell growth and proliferation (Table 2). However, PCL, PCL:CA, and PCL:CAP blends tend to better stimulate the proliferation of these cells than the remaining scaffolds. Curiously, on day 1, PCL:CA and PCL:CAP fibers were stained by DiOC₆(3). The most likely explanation for this is that DiOC₆(3), being a fluorescent and cationic dye,^[82] might have bound to the negative charges of the C=O groups of CA and CAP scaffolds. Since these have a higher negative charge than EC and MC, more nonspecific bonds of DiOC₆(3) to the CA and CAP scaffolds occur and a stronger green color is visible. From day 14 onwards, undulations in the cell monolayer comprised of areas with higher thickness interspersed with areas of lower thickness were detected on PCL, PCL:CAP, and PCL:MC and associated with villi-like structures.^[83] Therefore, typical mature small intestine cell features like polygonal and cobblestone^[53] as well as villi-like structures were observed for PCL, PCL:CAP, and PCL:MC, while, for the other scaffolds, all the previous features were observed except the villi-like structures.

Different results were obtained for lung epithelial cells: 16HBE and A549 cells did not grow in PCL:CAP scaffolds, and the latter cell line also failed to proliferate in PCL:EC formulations. PCL:MC seemed to produce the best results in A549 cells, indicating these may grow preferably in more hydrophilic surfaces, which is in accordance with previous reports.^[84,85]

Table 2. Summary of PCL:cellulose derivative electrospun scaffold performance in intestinal, skin, and lung models.

Epithelial model	Cell line	Type of scaffold				
		PCL	PCL:CA	PCL:CAP	PCL:EC	PCL:MC
Intestine	Caco-2	++	+	++	+	+
Skin	3T3	+	++	++	-	+
	XB2	+	++	++	-	+
Lung	16HBE	+	+	-- ^{a)}	+	+
	A549	+	+	-- ^{a)}	-- ^{a)}	++

^{a)}Pilot data not shown.

Indeed, A549 cell culture on hydrophobic scaffolds has led to the formation of spheroids instead of 2D monolayers, given the weak cell adhesion on these surfaces.^[86] Conversely, 16HBE cells behaved similarly in PCL:CA, PCL:EC, and PCL:MC scaffolds (Table 2). However, it became clear that both cell lines grew quite slowly in all formulations, and 16HBE cells were unable to survive the second week of in vitro culture in all electrospun mats, with the exception of plain PCL. Likewise, a reduction in A549 cell metabolic activity was registered between days 1 and 3 of culture, even though cells were then able to recover and proliferate up to 14 days in vitro. All in all, these results demonstrate that PCL and PCL:cellulose derivative scaffolds are not ideal for 16HBE and A549 in vitro culture under the conditions tested. It should be noted that, despite the positive outcomes generally elicited in Caco-2 epithelial cells, the wettability of all electrospun substrates is not ideal for cell adhesion and growth, as detailed previously, which may partly explain the unsatisfactory responses generated in 16HBE and A549 epithelial cells. It is possible that further optimization of cell seeding densities and culture times, for example, will achieve more promising results. Alternatively, coating PCL and PCL:cellulose derivative fibrous matrices with ECM-derived proteins, such as collagen or gelatin, may effectively stimulate cellular recognition and result in greater cell adhesion and proliferation.^[84,87]

While the available literature on the specific effects of surface topography and scaffold physicochemical properties on the behavior of 16HBE and A549 cells is quite limited, the potential of electrospun scaffolds for lung cell culture and growth has been previously demonstrated.^[86,88–90] Poly(lactic-co-glycolic acid) electrospun meshes were employed in a lung-on-chip device, in which co-culture of A549 cells, human fetal lung fibroblasts (HFL1 cell line), and human umbilical vein endothelial cells (HUVECs) was attained.^[91] Likewise, A549 cells have already been cultured in blend poly(vinyl alcohol) and collagen electrospun fibers, further showing how the combination of synthetic and natural biomaterials is an effective strategy to generate biocompatible and cell-instructive scaffolds.^[88] Another lung adenocarcinoma alveolar epithelial cell line, NCI-H441, has been successfully grown in hybrid matrices of gelatin and oxycellulose generated by needleless electrospinning,^[92] and its co-culture with ISO-HAS-1 endothelial cells and THP-1 macrophages on collagen-coated PCL electrospun meshes has also been reported.^[93] Regarding 16HBE cells, it was only possible to find a single paper exploring the growth of this cell line on electrospun scaffolds, in which collagen-coated, iron oxide nanoparticle-doped polyurethane nanofibers allowed 16HBE proliferation and epithelial differentiation.^[87] Nevertheless, previous work with distinct bronchial epithelial cell lines, such as Calu-3, supports the potential of these fibrous matrices for lung cell growth.^[94]

Finally, the studies on skin cell models produced markedly different results compared with the intestinal and lung cell models. Although several studies have shown the potential of pristine PCL^[65] and PCL-based electrospun nano/microfibers scaffolds for culturing skin cells,^[95–101] especially in the context of wound healing, few have considered PCL:cellulose composites.^[79,102–106] For example, Huang et al.^[103] prepared tri-layer nanofibrous scaffolds from PCL, CA, and chitosan that have been shown to promote adhesion, spreading, proliferation, segregation, and basal membrane production of human keratinocytes and fibroblasts

under *in vitro* culture and also after *in vivo* implantation in both mouse and pig models. These demonstrated that a combination of PCL and CA into a tri-layered interwoven nanofibrous construct can mimic the features of natural basal membranes and promote skin tissue regeneration and wound healing. Further studies using PCL and MC mixed fibers crosslinked with Manuka honey and applied as a biodegradable platform to deliver bioactive glass particles also showed great potential for the culture of human dermal fibroblasts and human keratinocyte-like HaCaT cells, in terms of cell viability, cell adhesion and migration through the substrates.^[79]

For dermal cells, the metabolic activity results of the present study suggest that given enough time for fibroblast proliferation on the fibrous substrates, most of the prepared scaffolds, especially PCL:CA and PCL:CAP, can effectively promote fibroblasts' metabolic activity. In fact, only fibroblasts seeded on scaffolds prepared from the PCL:EC blend showed a consistently lower metabolic activity throughout the entire culture period. In terms of cell proliferation, PCL:CA, PCL:CAP, and plain PCL scaffolds resulted in the highest dsDNA contents until 1-week of *in vitro* culture, which is indicative of increased fibroblast proliferation on these substrates and suggests that the hydrophobic nature of these materials does not impact 3T3 cell growth. Interestingly, on day 14, cells seeded on PCL:MC scaffolds showed dsDNA amounts comparable to the previous scaffolds, which supports the hypothesis that fibroblasts could also proliferate on hydrophilic substrates.

As for XB2 cells, PCL:CA and PCL:CAP scaffolds outperformed all others in terms of promoting keratinocytes' metabolic activity and proliferation. In fact, for all time points tested, keratinocytes seeded on PCL:CA and PCL:CAP fibrous meshes exhibited significantly higher metabolic activity and dsDNA content, compared to the other PCL:cellulose blends and plain PCL mats. This was also corroborated by the cells' internal membranes fluorescent staining, given that keratinocytes seeded on cellulose ester derivatives exhibited a homogenous distribution throughout the surface, as well as a typical cobblestone morphology. Similarly to 3T3 cells, PCL:EC and PCL:MC mats led to an uneven keratinocyte distribution and the formation of cell agglomerates throughout the substrate. While the poor wettability of PCL:EC mats may have contributed to cell clustering, other factors must have played a preponderant role in cell morphology and distribution, since PCL, PCL:CA, and PCL:CAP formulations displayed similar hydrophobicity but presented distinct cell morphology. On PCL:MC, this behavior might be related to its high hydrophilicity (null contact angle after 60 s, Figure 4) and diminished protein adsorption abilities, which in turn can result in slower cell attachment, delayed spreading and weaker cell engagement with the surface,^[107–109] as seen for fibroblasts and keratinocytes cultured onto PCL:MC meshes. Indeed, different studies have shown that the adsorption of protein components (e.g., ECM-derived proteins,^[110–113] platelet-derived growth factors^[65,66,114–117]) to the electrospun substrates is crucial for supporting fibroblast and keratinocyte proliferation, adhesion and spreading. The selective adsorption of adhesion molecules to the nanofibers and subsequent improvement of its cell adhesion potential depends not only on the materials' wettability, but also on many other physicochemical properties, including topography (e.g., mesh porosity, pore size, fiber diameter, and orientation), structural and mechanical features, chemical composition, among other factors,^[60,118] making it complex

to understand the scaffolds' adhesion capacity based only on their hydrophilicity. Overall, the results revealed that for both 3T3 and XB2 cells, PCL:CA and PCL:CAP were superior in terms of supporting cell mitochondrial activity, growth, and homogenous distribution on the electrospun scaffolds (Table 2).

Intriguingly, there was not a direct relationship between the scaffolds' physicochemical properties detailed in the present work and cell behavior. It would be interesting to observe how the scaffolds' physicochemical and mechanical properties change along with culture time, and to what degree each polymer component dissolves in culture media. Mechanical testing and degradation studies might also help determine whether these factors may have played an important role in the observed cellular responses. In a second step, further experiments addressing more tissue-specific endpoints should be carried out to assess the influence of the scaffold types on the characteristic tissue functions. Likewise, it was *not* tested whether any solvent residues might be retained in the nanofibrous scaffolds, which may cause toxic effects upon release into the culture medium.^[119–121] To address this potential cytotoxicity of PCL and PCL:cellulose derivative electrospun scaffolds, LIVE/DEAD assays based on viable and nonviable cell-selective permeability to fluorescent dyes could be performed at several timepoints during *in vitro* culture.^[119,122] Moreover, it would be beneficial to incubate all cells with leachates from all scaffold formulations, in order to assess whether any toxic products are released from the nanofibers into the culture media.^[119] Of note, only basic biocompatibility analyses were conducted, and it would be interesting to further evaluate the performance of these formulations in terms of tissue functionality (i.e., gene and protein expression, tight junction formation).

In general, the electrospun membrane formulations developed herein have demonstrated potential for epithelial and fibroblast cell culture and *in vitro* modeling of intestinal, skin, and pulmonary tissue (Table 2). Importantly, it became evident that distinct cell lines respond differently to the various substrates, highlighting the importance of fine-tuning scaffold properties according to the specific needs of the target tissue or organ. Further investigation on epithelial cell differentiation and function will be necessary to evaluate the performance of these biomaterials as platforms for *in vitro* tissue modeling, pharmaceutical, and toxicological research.

4. Conclusion

All PCL and cellulose-derivative blends enabled the generation of nonwoven, beadless electrospun scaffolds using a high-throughput, needleless electrospinning technique. A few differences in terms of physicochemical characteristics could be identified between the distinct formulations: electrospinning of PCL, PCL:CA, and PCL:EC solutions predominantly resulted in the generation of nanofibers, while a combination of nano- and microfibers was produced by PCL:CAP and PCL:MC blends. All electrospun formulations were considerably hydrophobic, with mean water contact angle values over 120°, except for PCL:MC, of which the initial mean contact angle of 94.5° rapidly decreased to 0° over the course of 60 s. *In vitro*, intestinal, skin, and lung cells demonstrated different behavior when cultured on

Figure 10. High-throughput needleless electrospinning experimental setup. A) Schematic representation of InoSPIN needleless linear blade electrode device. B) InoSPIN needleless electrospinning photograph: 1) rotating collector; 2) blade electrode; 3) moving element; 4) tube feeding the polymer solution and connected to a syringe.

Figure 11. Schematics of InoMatrix inserts containing electrospun scaffolds for intestinal and lung cell culture.

PCL and PCL:cellulose-derivative fibrous mats. All scaffolds supported Caco-2 colorectal epithelial cell growth, proliferation, and adhesion in an approximately similar way, although PCL and PCL:CAP tended to exhibit superior performance. Accordingly, PCL:CAP was also the formulation that produced the most promising results in XB2 keratinocytes and 3T3 fibroblasts, together with PCL:CA. Notwithstanding these observations, PCL:CAP was not capable of promoting lung epithelial cell growth, and PCL:EC failed to support A549 cell adhesion and proliferation. 16HBE cells grew similarly in all remaining polymer blends, whereas PCL:MC stood out by promoting higher levels of A549 cell metabolic activity and proliferation. Hence, it is possible to conclude that PCL and cellulose-derived materials have

demonstrated potential for in vitro epithelial tissue culture. Complementary analyses evaluating cell differentiation, gene and protein expression, and specialized function will be necessary to fully assess how these biomaterials can be applied in in vitro tissue and organ modeling and preclinical drug development.

5. Experimental Section

Materials: Acetic acid ($\geq 99\%$) and formic acid ($\geq 98\%$) were purchased from VWR. PCL, CA, CAP, EC, and MC (Methocel A15 LV) were acquired from Sigma-Aldrich, and PLA from Corbion. Human colorectal adenocarcinoma cells (Caco-2 cells, ACC169, HTB-37 clone from the German Collection of Microorganisms and Cell Cultures GmbH) were kindly provided by E. Fröhlich from the Medical University of Graz (Graz, Austria) and human bronchial epithelial cells (16HBE14o- cell line) by Prof. R. Bals at Saarland University (Germany). Human lung adenocarcinoma alveolar epithelial cells (A549, ACC-107 cell line) were purchased from the DSMZ German Collection of Microorganisms and Cell Cultures GmbH (Heidelberg, Germany). Immortalized murine keratinocytes (XB2 cell line)^[123] were acquired from the Wellcome Trust Functional Genomics Cell Bank (St. George's, University of London, UK), and immortalized murine fibroblasts (3T3-A31 cell line)^[124] were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich. Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Medium (DMEM) with high glucose (4.5 g L^{-1}) was purchased from Gibco Life Technologies (Thermo Fisher Scientific). DMEM/Nutrient Mixture F12 (DMEM:F12, 1:1) containing L-Glutamine and 15 mM HEPES and RPMI 1640 culture medium with L-Glutamine were acquired from Thermo Fisher Scientific. DMEM and non-essential amino acids solution (NEAA, $100\times$) were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich. Fetal bovine serum (FBS) and FBS Superior were purchased from Gibco Life Technologies (Thermo Fisher Scientific) or Sigma-Aldrich. Penicillin/Streptomycin (Pen/Strep, $10\,000 \text{ IU mL}^{-1}$ and $10\,000 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$, respectively) was acquired from Gibco Life Technologies (Thermo Fisher Scientific) or Sigma-Aldrich. CellTiter96 Aqueous One Solution Cell Proliferation Assay was purchased from Promega. Quant-iT dsDNA High-Sensitivity Assay and Quant-iT PicoGreen dsDNA Quantification Assay were acquired from Thermo Fisher Scientific. 3,3'-Dihydroxyoxycarbonyaniline iodide ($\text{DiOC}_6(3)$), ActinGreen 488 and NucBlue Fixed Cell ReadyProbes Reagents were purchased from Invitrogen (Thermo Fisher Scientific), and propidium iodide (PI) from Sigma-Aldrich.

Fabrication of Electrospun Nanofibrous Scaffolds: 20% w/v PCL, CA, CAP, and EC solutions and 10% w/v MC solutions were prepared in a 1:1 mixture of acetic acid and formic acid (AA:FA). PCL and cellulose derivative

blends were achieved by mixing 20 mL of a PCL solution with 15 mL of CA, CAP, EC, or MC solutions, to which 5 mL of chloroform and 10 mL of 1:1 AA:FA solvent mixture were subsequently added. Solutions were mixed by magnetic stirring and used for electrospinning. Fibrous scaffolds were generated through a needleless electrospinning technique, making use of a custom-made, lab-scale electrospinning unit (InoSPIN MINI, InoCure s.r.o., Celákovice, Czech Republic, **Figure 10**). The setup included a curved blade electrode (45 cm long, 0.3 cm wide, 5 cm radius) with a moving solution deposition element, a syringe pump, a rotating drum collector (10 cm diameter, rotating at 600 rpm), and two power supplies connected to both the collector and the electrode. The device was controlled using integrated software. A 20 mL plastic syringe containing the polymeric electrospinning solutions was fixed into the syringe pump, and the solution was pushed through the connected Teflon tube to the blade at a flow rate of 55 mL h⁻¹, until the first drop was observed on the blade surface. The process was initiated by turning on the voltage on the blade and collector: after optimization studies, a positive voltage of +60 kV (on the blade) and a negative voltage of -30 kV (on the collector) were used, and the distance between the collector and the blade was set at 110 mm. For all experiments, the solution was deposited over the 300 mm distance using an element moving rate of 40–50/100/100 mm s⁻¹. For easier removal of the samples, the nanofibers were deposited on baking paper wrapped around the rotating drum. A total of 20 mL of each polymeric solution was electrospun. Temperature and relative humidity inside the chamber were controlled using an integrated InoCool climate control unit (InoCure s.r.o., Celákovice, Czech Republic) and set to 45 °C and 10%, respectively.

For lung and intestinal cell culture, PCL, PCL:CA, PCL:CAP, PCL:EC, and PCL:MC electrospun fibrous membranes were cut into circular disks using a CO₂ laser and mounted on InoMatrix systems (InoCure s.r.o., Celákovice, Czech Republic), consisting of 3D-printed PLA inserts around which the scaffolds are fixed with a 3D-printed PLA ring, thereby mimicking the disposition of commercially available cell culture inserts (**Figure 11**). Conversely, for skin cell culture, the electrospun scaffolds were cut into 6 mm diameter circles using the CO₂ laser for further use in standard 96-well cell culture plates. Sterilization for cell culture was carried out using ethylene oxide (ÚVN Střešovice, Prague, Czech Republic).

SEM Imaging: Fiber morphology was characterized with a VEGA3 scanning electron microscope (Tescan, Czech Republic), using backscatter electron detectors (BSDs). Before analysis, samples were placed on pin holders with carbon tape and sputter-coated with gold particles using a Q150R S Rotary Pumped Coater System (Quorum Technologies). Fiber diameter and pore area of the samples were analyzed by manual measurements using Fiji/ImageJ v1.51 (National Institutes of Health (NIH), Bethesda, MD, USA).

For scaffold thickness measurements, electrospun meshes were cut in half for cross-sectional imaging. Each part was fixed onto the sample holder in a direction vertical to the SEM viewing axis and covered with a 30 nm thin gold layer (sputtering unit Univex 450B, Leybold GmbH, Cologne, Germany). SEM images were produced with a Zeiss EVO MA 10 microscope (Carl Zeiss AG, Oberkochen, Germany), using an acceleration voltage of 10 kV, an 800-fold magnification, and an angle of the sample stage in the range 4.3°–5.4°.

FTIR Analysis: To confirm the presence and possibly identify chemical interactions between PCL and the cellulose derivatives, FTIR analysis was performed using a Bruker Tensor-27 FTIR spectrometer. After the background signal was checked, the electrospun samples were folded 4 times in order to ensure a proper signal and placed on the diamond surface. Isopropanol was used to clean the surface in between each sample. Mid-infrared radiation (MIR) was selected as an optical source and the absorbance was set as a resulting spectrum mode with a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹ and a sample and background scan time of 32 scans. The FTIR spectra of all scaffolds were recorded in the range of 500 to 4000 cm⁻¹. Raw data were processed with OriginPro (v8.5.1) software. The baseline signal was removed from all data and the spectra were processed with a smoothing filter (Savitsky-Golay method, 50 points of window, polynomial order 4), after which absorbance peaks were calculated using the local maximum method. Final absorbance values were also plotted using OriginPro software.

Contact Angle Measurements: Contact angles were measured at 0, 10, 30, and 60 s after depositing a 3 µL distilled water droplet on the scaffolds'

surface using a drop shape analyzer (Krüss DSA100E), based on the static sessile drop mode at room temperature (RT). The contact angle was geometrically defined as the angle formed by a liquid at the three-phase boundary where liquid, gas, and solid intersect, and calculated using the Young–Laplace equation.

Adherent Cell Culture: Caco-2 cells (passages 10 to 20) were grown on tissue culture polystyrene (TCPS) flasks in DMEM with high glucose (4.5 g L⁻¹) supplemented with 10% v/v FBS, 1% v/v Pen/Strep (100 IU mL⁻¹ and 100 µg mL⁻¹, respectively) and 1% v/v NEAA solution at 37 °C under a 5% CO₂ humidified atmosphere, according to the protocol described by Schimpel et al.^[125] Culture medium was refreshed every 2 days.

Immortalized XB2 keratinocytes (passage 17) and immortalized 3T3 fibroblasts (passage 13) were grown in TCPS flasks with DMEM with high glucose (4.5 g L⁻¹) supplemented with 10% v/v FBS and 1% v/v Pen/Strep at 37 °C under a 10% CO₂ humidified atmosphere, according to the manufacturer's protocol. Culture media were refreshed every 3 days.

16HBE cells (passages 18 to 25) were grown in TCPS flasks with DMEM:F12 (1:1) containing L-Glutamine and 15 mM HEPES, supplemented with 10% v/v FBS Superior and 1% v/v Pen/Strep, at 37 °C under a 5% CO₂ humidified atmosphere. A549 cells (passages 18 to 22) were grown in TCPS flasks with RPMI 1640 culture medium containing L-Glutamine, supplemented with 10% v/v FBS Superior and 1% v/v Pen/Strep, at 37 °C under a 5% CO₂ humidified atmosphere. Culture media were refreshed every 2 days for both cell lines.

Cell line quality control followed the American Type Culture Collection (ATCC) recommendations: cells were routinely tested for mycoplasma contamination and growth curve analyses were performed. Cells were visually examined before every experiment to observe cell morphology and exclude the presence of bacterial contaminations.

Biocompatibility Studies: To assess the biocompatibility of the electrospun scaffolds toward intestinal, skin, and lung cell models, different biological studies were performed at specific time points of cell culture under optimized conditions.

Cell Seeding Procedure—Intestinal Model: Caco-2 cells were seeded at a density of 637 000 cells cm⁻² onto electrospun fibrous scaffolds mounted on 24-well InoMatrix inserts (inner diameter: 10 mm). 300 µL of fresh culture medium was applied on the insert's apical side and 600 µL on the basolateral side. Subsequently, cells were incubated at 37 °C and 5% CO₂, exchanging the medium every second day. In total, cells were kept under culture for up to 21 days.

Cell Seeding Procedure—Skin Model: Epidermal keratinocytes (XB2 cells) or dermal fibroblasts (3T3 cells) were seeded at a density of 31 250 cells cm⁻² in 50 µL of culture medium. Cells were incubated for 2 h in a CO₂-humidified atmosphere (37 °C, 10% CO₂) to promote cell attachment to the electrospun matrices, after which 200 µL of fresh culture medium was added per well. Culture media were refreshed once every 3 days and cells were kept under culture for up to 14 days.

Cell Seeding Procedure—Lung Model: 16HBE or A549 cells were seeded onto the apical compartments of InoMatrix inserts at a density of 50 000 cells cm⁻² in 100 µL of culture medium, with 600 µL of medium in the basolateral side. Cells were incubated in a humidified incubator for 1 h at 37 °C, 5% CO₂ to allow for some level of cell attachment to the electrospun matrices, after which 200 µL of fresh culture medium was added to the apical compartment. Culture media were refreshed once every 2 days and cells were kept under culture for up to 14 days.

Cell Metabolic Activity: The metabolic activity of the cells seeded on the electrospun scaffolds was assessed using the CellTiter 96 Aqueous One Solution Reagent (MTS assay) according to the manufacturer's instructions on days 1, 3, 7, and 14 of the experiment, in the case of skin and pulmonary cell models. For the intestinal cell model, day 21 was also tested. Briefly, cell-seeded scaffolds and InoMatrix inserts were incubated with a mixture of MTS reagent and cell culture media at a volume ratio of 1:5 for 2 h (skin and lung cells) or 4 h (intestinal cells). Absorbance values were recorded with a spectrophotometer at 490 nm, from which background absorbance values at 690 nm were subtracted.

Cell Proliferation: Cell-seeded scaffolds were immersed in cell lysis buffer (0.2% v/v Triton X-100, 10 mM Tris, 1 mM EDTA) and subjected to three freeze–thaw–vortex cycles for DNA extraction. The proliferation

of the cells seeded on the electrospun scaffolds was evaluated based on dsDNA quantification and assessed using the Quant-iT dsDNA High-Sensitivity Assay (intestinal and skin cells) or Quant-iT PicoGreen dsDNA Quantification Assay (lung cells) kits according to the manufacturer's instructions. dsDNA quantification analyses were carried out on days 1, 3, 7, and 14 of the experiment for skin and pulmonary cell models and days 1, 3, 7, 14, and 21 for intestinal cell models.

In all cell metabolic activity and proliferation experiments, cell-free scaffolds incubated in parallel and processed similarly to those with cells were used as blanks and their background absorbance or fluorescence values were subtracted.

Cell Adhesion, Distribution, and Morphology—Intestinal and Skin Models: DiOC₆(3) staining was used to observe cell adhesion, distribution, and morphology on days 1, 7, 14, and 21 (intestinal cells) and 1, 7, and 14 (skin cells). Cells were fixed with ice-cold methyl alcohol (−20 °C) for 10 min. Subsequently, the DiOC₆(3) fluorescence probe was added at a concentration of 1 μg mL^{−1} and incubated for 30 min at RT, protected from light. After washing with PBS, the samples were incubated with propidium iodide (PI, 5 μg mL^{−1}) for 10 min at RT in the dark. Finally, all scaffolds were thoroughly rinsed with PBS, transferred onto glass microscope slides, and, in the case of intestinal cell culture, covered with a fluorescent mounting medium (Dako, Agilent Technologies). Visualization was performed using a confocal laser scanning microscope (CLSM). λ_{ex} = 488 and 560 nm and λ_{em} = 520 and 580 nm were used for DiOC₆(3) and PI detection, respectively. For intestinal cell models, CLSM imaging was performed using a Zeiss LSM 510 META confocal microscope (Carl Zeiss GmbH, Jena, Germany) equipped with a ZEN2008 software package and Z-sections were acquired with a plan-Neofluar 40×/1.3 Oil DIC objective. Conversely, for skin cell models, CLSM imaging was performed using a ZEISS LSM 5 DUO confocal microscope (Carl Zeiss GmbH, Jena, Germany) and a plan-Apochromat 20×/0.8 NA objective. The resulting Z-stacks were processed with Fiji/ImageJ software v1.51.

Cell Adhesion, Distribution, and Morphology—Lung Model: 16HBE and A549 cell adhesion and morphology on the electrospun scaffolds were evaluated by cytoskeleton and nuclei staining with ActinGreen 488 and NucBlue Fixed Cell ReadyProbes Reagents, respectively, on days 1, 7, and 14 of culture. All steps were performed on a shaker. After a brief wash with PBS, cells were fixed with 10% formalin solution for 15 min at RT. Following fixation, cells were washed thrice with PBS and permeabilized with 0.2% v/v Triton X-100 in PBS for 15 min at RT. Next, scaffolds were washed twice with PBS and ActinGreen solution in PBS was added, followed by a 30 min incubation in the dark. ActinGreen solution was then removed and replaced by NucBlue solution in PBS, after which cells were incubated for 10 min in the dark. Finally, scaffolds were washed twice with PBS, mounted on glass microscope slides with Eprelia Immu-Mount mounting medium (Thermo Fisher Scientific), and stored at 4 °C until imaging. CLSM imaging was performed using a Leica TCS SP8 confocal microscope coupled to LAS-X software (Leica Microsystems, Wetzlar, Germany) and a plan-Apochromat 20×/0.75 NA multi-immersion objective, and Z-projections were obtained using Fiji/Image J software v1.51.

Statistical Analysis: Data are represented as mean ± standard deviation (SD). Statistical analysis was carried out using GraphPad Prism 9.1.1 software (San Diego, CA, USA). For normally distributed data, comparisons were performed with the one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Tukey's multiple comparison tests for samples with homogeneous variances. Data presenting a non-Gaussian distribution were evaluated with the nonparametric Kruskal–Wallis test, followed by Dunn's post hoc analysis. Two-tailed significance levels were considered, and results were found statistically significant for *p*-values < 0.05. Levels of significance were represented as follows: **p* < 0.05, ***p* < 0.01, ****p* < 0.001, *****p* < 0.0001. Symbols *, #, +, †, and Δ were used for days 1, 3, 7, 14, and 21.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Keywords

3R principle, cellulose, electrospinning, epithelial barrier, in vitro models, toxicological screening

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